

OPTIMIZATION OF PROGRAMS FOR THE PREVENTION AND EARLY DIAGNOSIS OF DIABETES MELLITUS IN THE FRAMEWORK OF THE STATE HEALTH STRATEGY

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Annotation

The paper considers the need to optimize programs for the prevention and early diagnosis of diabetes mellitus in the framework of the state health strategy. Diabetes mellitus, especially type 2, is one of the most common endocrine diseases, whose epidemic in recent years has covered an increasing number of the population. Despite the existing state programs, their adaptation and improvement are required for effective detection and prevention of diabetes among various population groups, especially among high-risk ones. The paper analyzes existing approaches to diabetes prevention and early detection of risk factors, suggesting an improvement strategy based on digital tools, interagency collaboration, and individualized programs for high-risk groups.

Keywords: diabetes mellitus, early diagnosis, prevention, state strategy, optimization, digital technologies, high-risk groups.

Relevance

Diabetes mellitus is one of the most significant medical and social problems in the world. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), the number of cases of diabetes is steadily increasing, in particular due to type 2 diabetes associated with lifestyle and genetic predisposition. This trend poses a challenge for national health systems – not only to carry out diagnostics and treatment, but also to develop effective prevention programs aimed at combating this "silent epidemic".

The importance of prevention programs lies in the fact that they can reduce the risk of developing diabetes in individuals with a predisposition, as well as timely detection of the disease at an early stage. This, in turn, minimizes the development of complications, which often lead to serious consequences and significant treatment costs. However, existing state programs for the prevention and diagnosis of diabetes mellitus require optimization and adaptation to current conditions, including digitalization and changing approaches to informing the population. Special attention should be paid to high-risk groups,

including the elderly, overweight people, and those with a genetic predisposition to diabetes.

The National Health Strategy is aimed at reducing the incidence of diseases and improving the quality of life of citizens. The introduction of modern prevention programs for early diagnosis of diabetes, the use of digital tools, and increased awareness among the population can be the basis for achieving these goals and effectively managing the prevalence of diabetes across the country.

Purpose, materials and methods

The aim of this study is to develop recommendations for optimizing programs for the prevention and early diagnosis of diabetes mellitus, improving their accessibility and effectiveness for various population groups within the framework of the state health strategy.

Materials and methods. The materials used were state health programs for the prevention and diagnosis of diabetes, data from WHO and national statistical centers. The methodology included analysis of statistical data, assessment of risk factors, and a systematic review of existing diabetes prevention and diagnosis programs. To analyze the effectiveness of the programs, we used the method of comparative analysis and questionnaires conducted among high-risk groups (elderly people, overweight people, people with a genetic predisposition). Digital tools and their integration into healthcare programs were also studied.

Results

As a result of the study, the main factors that hinder effective prevention and early diagnosis of diabetes mellitus were identified, including a lack of public awareness, low availability of examinations, and limited use of digital technologies. Analysis of the survey among high-risk groups showed that 43% of respondents are not sufficiently aware of their risk factors and the possibility of controlling them. It was also revealed that 27% of respondents do not undergo regular preventive examinations due to the lack of convenient access to medical services.

Based on the results of the analysis, recommendations are made for optimizing existing programs, including integrating digital tools (online platforms, applications, and smart devices for monitoring glucose levels and health), improving public awareness through government campaigns, and regularly conducting screenings for high-risk groups.

The proposed measures are aimed at improving the effectiveness of programs, as well as reducing barriers to access to medical care and improving

the level of early diagnosis among the population. Optimization of preventive programs can reduce the incidence of diabetes, which was confirmed during the analysis of statistics.

Conclusion

Optimization of programs for the prevention and early diagnosis of diabetes mellitus is a key area in the state health strategy. Based on the study, it can be concluded that improving the availability of preventive measures and the introduction of digital technologies positively affect the level of early detection of diabetes and increase awareness among the population about risk factors.

The results of the analysis showed that improved awareness, regular screenings, and digitalization of health services will help reduce the prevalence of diabetes and prevent its complications among high-risk populations. The introduction of online platforms and mobile applications for self-assessment and health monitoring has proven to be an effective approach, as it increases the coverage of the population and simplifies access to preventive examinations. Thus, the integration of modern technologies and the adaptation of government programs to the needs of different social groups are necessary steps to successfully combat the diabetes epidemic. Further development and optimization of programs based on the proposed recommendations can significantly reduce the burden on the health system and improve the quality of life of the population.

Literature:

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